

A GLOBAL MOSAIC FROM COPERNICUS SENTINEL-1 DATA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an algorithmic workflow for producing mosaics based on the dual polarisation capability of Sentinel-1 SAR imagery. The main characteristics of the specific method are: automated and nonparametric approach, fast processing, incremental adjustment and information distinction. The workflow has been optimized according to the configuration of the recently introduced JEODPP platform. Challenges, suggestions and solutions are discussed as well.

Index Terms— Mosaic, Sentinel-1, Copernicus, histogram discretization

1. INTRODUCTION

Sentinel-1 (S1) space mission is a constituent project designed and managed by the European Space Agency (ESA) within the framework of the Copernicus programme [2]. Technically, it is a constellation of two satellites, Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B, sharing the same orbital plane with a 180° orbital phasing difference, aiming at acquiring systematically and providing routinely data and information products to Copernicus Ocean, Land, and Emergency as well as to national user services.

Generating and assembling composites from satellite imagery is of great importance, giving birth to applications ranging from the construction of a base-layer to more sophisticated processes like the spatio-temporal signal comparison and analysis. Mosaicking is the process of stitching together image tiles which have a unique spatio-temporal stamp for generating a seamless, homogeneous canvas. Since the launch of S1A mission, various S1-mosaics have been generated at national and regional levels such as [5, 1, 3, 4].

This paper describes an algorithmic workflow for building mosaics based on S1 data, following a fully automated and nonparametric approach, suitable for being executed in a high-throughput computing facility. It can be considered equally as a demonstration of a real application supporting efficient handling and processing of big Earth observation data.

2. THE JEODPP PLATFORM

The experiments and the processing have been done on a high-throughput computational platform called the Joint

Research Centre Earth Observation Data and Processing Platform (JEODPP) [12, 13]. The main components of the JEODPP infrastructure are presented briefly below:

- storage system: based on Just a Bunch of Disks (JBODs) managed by *EOS* open-source distributed file system [9] developed and maintained by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN);
- processing servers and related services: a high performance commodity cluster at which a flexible scheduler (HTCondor [8]) undertakes the task of distributing the load over processing servers connected to the storage servers administered by *EOS*;
- network system: storage and metadata servers are connected via (single or double) bonded network configuration;
- virtualisation: Docker containers [11] allow for flexible management of hardware resources and processing environments. They function as a light-weight type of virtualisation to separate processing instances.
- user interface: two web-based modes are provided to the user for fast prototyping and analytics via i) remote desktop supported by the Apache Guacamole gateway, and ii) interactive visualization and on the fly processing through Jupyter notebooks and in-house hard-coded libraries.

3. DATA

The application for which the data were designated is the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) project [7] and more specifically, the generation of a global built-up map based on S1 data [10]. The dataset consists of 5,026 Sentinel-1A products (~8TB) covering almost completely the globe, spanning over the year of 2016, acquired in IW (Interferometric Wide swath) mode, processed in GRDH format, and coming in dual polarisation (mostly VV+VH). The data were queried and downloaded using OpenSearch and OData scripting capabilities offered by the Copernicus Service hub [6] operated by the ESA.

The objective of the presented work was the use of the aforementioned dataset for the generation of a homogeneous base-layer; in that way, the user can easily contrast the input S1 imagery and the GHSL output and assess better the results.

4. PROCESSING WORKFLOW

Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) products are projected to ground range using an Earth ellipsoid model such as WGS84 (slant range coordinates), with pixel values representing detected magnitude. Calibration and geo-location takes place as a pre-processing step in our workflow, executed usually once per application. The main processing of image blending and mosaicking can have several flavours (different color compositions and mosaicking rules), therefore the entire processing workflow was split in two phases.

4.1. Pre-processing

The pre-processing was done via the S1 toolbox (S1TBX version 2.0.2) and comprises the following modules:

1. Apply orbit file: this file provides accurate satellite position and velocity information, based on which the orbit state vectors in the abstract metadata of the Sentinel-1 product are updated;
2. Thermal noise removal: using the noise vectors it removes dark strips near scene edges with invalid data. On the output of this process, we applied a mathematical morphology operation in order to cut off completely the uncertain borders;
3. Radiometric calibration: it computes the backscatter intensity (sigma nought) using sensor calibration parameters in the GRDH metadata;
4. Terrain correction (orthorectification): it converts data from ground range geometry into a map coordinate system. For the majority of the products we employed the SRTM 1 arc sec HGT DEM and for the remaining 548 products the ASTER 1 arc sec GDEM due to the non-exhaustive coverage of the SRTM. The resampling was done via the bilinear interpolation method.

Due to the need for bringing to light small targets like sparse settlements, we decided to omit the speckle filtering stage. Nevertheless, depending on the application, one can easily add this process (usually before step 4) since S1TBX already supports single product and multi-temporal speckle filtering.

4.2. Main-processing

The pre-processing outcome for each product is two geo-referenced images (backscatter coefficient for the two polarisations as floating-point) in WGS 84/Pseudo-Mercator coordinate system (EPSG:3857) with 19.11 spatial resolution, corresponding to the 13 zoom level in Tile Map Service (TMS). The main processing steps are as follows:

4.2.1. False color composition rules

The ability to visually differentiate built-up areas from other natural or man-made features depends on the optimal combination of bands that provides the maximum separability between those different features. The false colour composite proposed here uses the 8-bit discretization of the dual polar-

ization backscatter values as follows: the VH or HV as Red, a linear mapping over the average of (VH,VV) or (HV,HH) as Green, and the VV or HH respectively as Blue band.

1. Saturate the extreme values: Given that image $I_{X_i, i=1,2}$ denotes one of the two $\{VH, VV\}$ or $\{HV, HH\}$ polarizations with V: Vertical, H: Horizontal, apply the function

$$I_{X_i}(v) = \begin{cases} 1, & v > 1 \\ 10^{-4}, & -1 < v \leq 10^{-4} \\ v, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where -1 has been set as no data value. Even if the range of values after calibration/terrain correction is expected to lay out between 0 and 1, few negative values may be produced due to wrong operation of the thermal noise removal which is intended for scenes over land and not over the ocean. In the other side of the range, few values greater than 1 may be attributed to local strong scatterers. Without affecting the outcome, the function above set all the values to the expected range;

2. Compute the common data domain for the two polarisations by applying morphological operators to clean further the noisy/low value borders:

$$D = \bigcap_{X_i, i=1,2} \varepsilon_{N_{7 \times 7}} \left(\delta_{N_{5 \times 5}} (D_{X_i}) \right), \text{ where } N_{7 \times 7}$$

and $N_{5 \times 5}$ are two structuring elements selected for making the area compact and for cropping the image borders sufficiently; the functions δ and ε correspond to the morphological operations of *dilation* and *erosion*. The binary images D_{X_i} have value 1 when for the corresponding values of $I_{X_i}(v)$ it holds $v > -1$ and 0 otherwise. Subsequently, the no data values of every I_{X_i} are being updated according to D ;

3. Convert each I_{X_i} to its logarithmic counterpart and discretize its values in 8-bits by binning appropriately the image values distribution: Even though the standard practice is to transform to db via the function $10 \cdot \log_{10}(\cdot)$, in this case any kind of logarithmic function is producing equivalent result. The natural logarithm spreads intuitively the values without the multiplication by an extra factor; hence, $I_{X_i}^l = \ln(I_{X_i})$. By analysing the statistical distributions (SD) of the continuous values of all the $I_{X_i}^l$, we estimated the following critical ranges and values: for cross polarizations, i) $h = [8, 124, 107, 14, 2]$, $r = \ln\left([10^{-4}, 10^{-2}, 0.035, 0.06, 0.12, 1]\right)$ when SD is close to normal, ii) $h = [8, 144, 87, 14, 2]$, $r = \ln\left([10^{-4}, 10^{-2}, 0.025, 0.06, 0.12, 1]\right)$ when SD is left-skewed, and for co-polarizations, iii) $h = [14, 122, 105, 12, 2]$, $r = \ln\left([10^{-4}, 0.04, 0.14, 0.32, 0.63, 1]\right)$ when SD is close to normal, iv) $h = [14, 142, 85, 12, 2]$, $r = \ln\left([10^{-4}, 0.04, 0.12, 0.32, 0.63, 1]\right)$ when SD is left-skewed. For each of the four cases, the respective h and r vectors steer

the recursive construction of a vector C which contains $|C| = 255$ values: $C = \bigcup_{k=1, \dots, 5} \left[r_{1,k}, r_{j+1,k} = r_{j,k} + \frac{r_{1,k+1} - r_{1,k}}{h_k - 1} \mid j = 1, \dots, h_k - 1 \right]$. Finally, by utilizing the C vector as being reversely ordered by the maximum to the minimum value, the data binning is being carried out as follows: $\forall v$ of $I_{X_i}^l : v < c_d \in C \Rightarrow B_{X_i}(v) = d$, where $d \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : 1 \leq d \leq 255$; c_d are the values of C used as thresholds over $I_{X_i}^l(v)$. $B_{X_i}(v)$ denotes the discrete representation of $I_{X_i}^l(v)$;

4. Generate the Green band by averaging the output of the previous step and scaling it by applying a gain and a bias: $\lceil \frac{Red+Blue}{2} \cdot 1.1 + 30 \rceil$. The gain and the bias inside the ceiling function aim at shifting the low to medium values of the Red and Blue bands that empirically appear to correspond in many cases to green areas, to higher levels of the green scale;
5. Crop the images in tiles of size $12,288 \times 12,288$ pixels: this operation is required in order to manipulate only the overlapped areas. The specific tile size was considered suitable in terms of I/O operations and file storage, while keeping in the same time enough information (samples) from the source image.

4.2.2. Tiles merging and rendering

This operation concerns the merging of the overlapped tiles. At tile level, an ordered list of images is being generated having as criterion the data domain size (in descending order). The first chosen tile (T_1 with data domain D_1) constitutes the canvas upon which the remaining tiles will be positioned. Next, the second tile (T_2 with data domain D_2) in the list is being read. Then, if $D_1 \cap D_2 = \emptyset \Rightarrow T_1 = T_1 \cup T_2$. Otherwise, the euclidean distance transform (DT) is computed over the binary array $D_c = D_1 \cap D_2$. The updated tile is composed as a weighted sum of the normalized DT , i.e. $T_1(D_c) = T_1(D_c) \odot (1 - DT(D_c) / \max(DT(D_c))) + T_2(D_c) \odot DT(D_c) / \max(DT(D_c))$, where the operator \odot signifies the pixel-wise multiplication. For the domain $D_n = \neg D_1 \cap D_2$, it holds $T_1(D_n) = T_2(D_n)$. Having only two tiles to process in the memory, this progressive operation turns to perform efficiently in terms of high-throughput computing, whilst allowing the incorporation of potentially new tiles without the need of re-processing big parts of the mosaic.

5. RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

The algorithm fits the way a high-throughput computing cluster operates by allowing task parallelization, modularity and efficient I/O handling. Fig.1 demonstrates the scalability of JEODPP when handling the SITBX with both multithreading and single thread options; the capacity is measured on how much input data can be read, processed and stored back to EOS per second. Fig.2 shows the total elapsed time for both processes of false color composition (652 concurrent jobs) and tiles merging (800 concurrent jobs). It is worth

Fig. 1. The JEODPP scalability while running the SITBX with multithreading enabled (left bars) and by setting 1 thread per core with the option `-q` of the `gpt` command (right bars).

mentioning that both processes can execute simultaneously on the cluster by setting appropriate job priorities, shortening thereby significantly the total elapsed time.

The main challenges regarding the tiles mosaicking with the aim to produce an homogeneous result were the seasonality and the dissimilar orbit direction as steady effects, and occasionally, the distinct values among the different areas of the same scene due to suboptimal de-bursting and merging of the sub-swaths, the presence of artifacts, the signal saturation and the inadequate operation of thermal noise removal. Fig. 3 displays four such indicative cases (products prefix: S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV). In the context of big data framework, exploiting all the available data covering a particular geographic area in a specific time span can lead to a better result due to the signal stability that inherently comes with the data redundancy (law of large numbers under the relaxed assumption of identically distributed measurements); this objective was out of the scope at the time of implementation.

An overview of the global S1-mosaic in the JEODPP interactive visualization is shown in Fig. 4. It is worth noting

Fig. 2. The total execution time for the two stages of the main processing displayed against the cluster CPU load in a total of 912 available processing cores.

Fig. 3. Irregular cases on the available imagery: (a) intense discrepancies between adjacent sub-swaths; (b) artifacts; (c) signal saturation; (d) seasonality effect.

that no ancillary data like water mask or land cover layers have been used; the outcome has been produced based on the selected S1 data only.

Fig. 5 shows a snapshot of the S1-mosaic overlaid by the derived GHSL product (red pixels). Observing the left image, built-up in white-cyan contrasts vividly with the greenish and brownish lowlands, as well as with the dark color of the lakes.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

We presented an algorithmic workflow for mosaicking Sentinel-1 images using a false color composition such that a built-up layer derived from these images can be contrasted well, allowing the user to identify easily strange or unexpected effects. Statistical analysis on the available data provides

Fig. 4. The global mosaic from Copernicus Sentinel-1A data (EPSG:3857) with 19.11 spatial resolution.

Fig. 5. Left: Example of S1-mosaic with built-up areas visible in bright blue; Right: Automatically extracted built-up areas from the GHSL displayed in red overlaying the S1-mosaic.

estimations that drive the discretization of the floating type images. Subsequently, the algorithm is executed in an automatic, nonparametric and progressive mode. As follow-up activity, we intend to focus on the optimization of the S1 product selection and on testing/adjusting on the fly false colour compositions through the interactive visualization.

7. REFERENCES

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